

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial studies of some 3d-metal complexes of chemotherapeutic importance

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Abstract : Complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with the Schiff bases 3-nitrobenzylidene-2,4-dinitroaniline (NDA), 3-nitrobenzylidene-4-aminoacetanilide (NAA) and 2-furfurylidene-2-nitroaniline (FNA) have been synthesized and their characterization have been done by microanalytical data, UV-Vis, IR, ESR spectroscopy, conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements. Ligand field parameters of some of the complexes have also been calculated. The complexes have also been screened for their antimicrobial potential against selected fungi and bacteria.

Keywords : Schiff base, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , synthesis, antimicrobial studies.

Introduction

The extensive use of common antibiotics in medicine has resulted in an increasing number of resistant strains of bacteria and other microbes, through mutation and gene transfer. This alarming and accelerating rate of resistance is posing life threatening status in millions of people worldwide. Rise of drug resistant microorganisms and new emerging diseases coupled with the toxicity and unavailability of advance generation drugs has necessitated the search for newer compounds namely Schiff bases with improved properties and extended antibacterial spectrum, towards the future resistant strains¹⁻⁵. Such studies provide the basis for developing functional models as anticancer, antimalarial, antifungal, antiviral and antibacterial metallo-pharmaceuticals. The metal complexes with Schiff bases find various biological and industrial applications. The complexes play an important role in biological systems where enzymes are known to be activated by metal ions³⁻⁶.

The present paper discusses the synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial studies of the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 3-nitrobenzylidene-2,4-dinitroaniline (NDA), 3-nitrobenzylidene-4-aminoacetanilide (NAA) and 2-furfurylidene-2-nitroaniline (FNA).

3-Nitrobenzylidene-2,4-dinitroaniline (NDA)

3-Nitrobenzylidene-4-aminoacetanilide (NAA)

Furfurylidene-2-nitroaniline (FNA)

Results and discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) of the complexes show that they have metal to ligand stoichiometry in 1 : 2. The molar conductance values of the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with NDA and NAA (in methanol 10^{-3} M) suggest their non-electrolytic nature while FNA complexes to be of 1 : 2 electrolytic nature^{2,7}. The weight loss on heating at 100 and 550 °C gives an idea about stoichiometry and thermal stability of the complexes (Table 2). The representative equation of synthesis of complexes is shown below :

FAB mass : The FAB mass spectra of the complexes have been studied as representative case. The intensities of these peaks give an idea about the stabilities of fragments. The FAB mass spectrum of [Co(NDA)₂Cl₂].H₂O

complex shows a molecular ion peak (m⁺) at *m/z* 778, which suggests the monomeric nature of the complex and confirm the proposed formula. Other peaks of appreciable intensity have been observed at *m/z* values 760, 724, 689,

Table 1. Analytical and magnetic data of the complexes

Compd.	Molecular and Empirical formula	Colour	Mol. wt. [m.p./(dec.)°C]	Yield (%)	Ω_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
L-I	NDA	Yellow	316.2	75	-	-
	C ₁₃ H ₈ N ₄ O ₆		(165)			
1	[Co(NDA) ₂ Cl ₂].H ₂ O	Dark green	778.3	66	47.3	4.60
	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ CoN ₈ O ₁₃		(182)			
2	[Ni(NDA) ₂ Cl ₂].2H ₂ O	Dirty yellow	798.1	65	32.1	Diamag.
	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ NiN ₈ O ₁₄		(190)			
3	[Cu(NDA) ₂ Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O	Greenish yellow	838.9	60	7.5	1.89
	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ CuN ₈ O ₁₆		(182)			
L-II	NAA	Dark green	283.3	80	-	-
	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃		(188)			
4	[Co(NAA) ₂ Cl ₂].2H ₂ O	Hena green	1425.0	65	49.0	5.05
	C ₆₀ H ₅₆ Cl ₄ Co ₂ N ₁₂ O ₁₄		(309)			
5	[Ni(NAA) ₂ Cl ₂] ₂	Yellowish green	1392.6	60	39.5	3 14
	C ₆₀ H ₅₂ Cl ₄ Ni ₂ N ₁₂ O ₁₂		(307)			
6	[Cu(NAA) ₂ Cl ₂].2H ₂ O	Black	1438.2	60	57.6	1.95
	C ₆₀ H ₅₆ Cl ₄ Cu ₂ N ₁₂ O ₁₄		(332)			
L-III	FNA	Reddish brown	216.2	50	-	-
	C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ O ₃		(102)			
7	[Co(FNA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	Sand stone	614.3	55	203.5	4.95
	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ CoN ₄ O ₉		(237)			
8	[Ni(FNA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	Dark olive green	616.1	50	189.6	3.10
	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ NiN ₄ O ₉		(204)			
9	[Co(FNA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	Dark brown	620.9	55	186.4	1.92
	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ CuN ₄ O ₉		(208)			

* All the compounds gave satisfactory % C, N and M results.

Table 2. Thermal decomposition of metal complexes (thermal data)

Compd.	Metal complex (Abbr. name)	% Remaining wt.; Obsd. (Calcd.)		
		Room temp.	100 °C	550 °C
1	Co ^{II} -NDA	100	95.4 (94.5)	13.2 (10.1)
2	Ni ^{II} -NDA	100	94.4 (92.3)	11.4 (9.3)
3	Cu ^{II} -NDA	100	94.8 (93.5)	9.0 (9.4)
4	Co ^{II} -NAA	100	96.2 (94.9)	6.2 (5.6)
5	Ni ^{II} -NAA	100	96.3 (95.1)	6.4 (5.2)
6	Cu ^{II} -NAA	100	96.9 (96.0)	6.9 (5.5)
7	Co ^{II} -FNA	100	96.8 (96.3)	11.9 (13.1)
8	Ni ^{II} -FNA	100	97.0 (95.8)	14.3 (12.1)
9	Cu ^{II} -FNA	100	96.5 (94.8)	13.9 (12.8)

597, 505, 352 and 112. The peak 689 corresponds to nearest composition $[\text{Co}(\text{NDA})_2]$ and 112 to cobalt chelated with $-\text{N}=\text{C}$ as ligand moiety.

The FAB mass spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{NAA})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ complex shows a molecular ion peak (m^+) at m/z 1392, which suggest the dimeric nature of the complex and confirm the proposed formula. Other peaks of appreciable intensity have been observed at m/z values 1250, 624, 532, 288, 136 and 114. The peak at 1250 corresponds to nearest composition $[\text{Ni}(\text{NAA})_2]$; 624 to $[\text{Ni}(\text{NAA})_2]$ and 114 to nickel chelated with $-\text{N}=\text{C}$ and $\text{O}=\text{C}$ donor as ligand moiety.

The FAB mass spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{FNA})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex shows a molecular ion peak (m^+) at m/z 620, which suggests the monomeric nature of the complex and confirm the proposed formula. Other peaks of appreciable intensity have been observed at m/z values 602, 566, 495, 251 and 172. The peak at 602 corresponds to nearest composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{FNA})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$; 566 to $[\text{Cu}(\text{FNA})_2]\text{Cl}_2$; 495 to $[\text{Cu}(\text{FNA})_2]$ and 172 to copper-chelated with $-\text{N}=\text{C}$ and $\text{O}=\text{C}$ donor as ligand moiety.

(i) *Complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 3-nitrobenzylidene-2,4-dinitroaniline (NDA) :*

The IR spectrum of ligand shows a strong band at 1622 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ (azomethine) group which shifts down ($1610 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes. This negative shift indicates the participation of azomethine groups in complexation^{2,8-10}. An intense band at 1525 cm^{-1} in ligand, remains unaffected in complexes, has been assigned to $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{O}}$ (stretching). A broad band around $3340 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of complexes is assignable to ν_{stret} of water. A band of medium intensity at $780 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_{OH} rocking)⁵, suggests the presence of coordinated water in Cu^{II} complex. This band is absent in the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The new band at $460 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ vibration in the complexes¹¹⁻¹⁶.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex exhibits bands at 16110 cm^{-1} (medium) and 11460 cm^{-1} (intense) assignable to transitions $^4A_2 - ^4T_1(F)$ and $^4A_2 - ^4T_1(P)$. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 4.60 B.M. On the basis of magnetic^{2,11,14,23} and electronic spectral data, the tetrahedral geometry has been suggested for this complex¹⁴⁻²⁰. Ni^{II} complex shows a band at 18550 cm^{-1} ,

assignable to $^1A_{1g} - ^1B_{2g}$ transition. The diamagnetic nature of complex indicates the geometry to be square planar¹⁴⁻²⁰. A broad band at around 13305 cm^{-1} in Cu^{II} complex has been assigned to $^2E_g - ^2T_{2g}$. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 1.89 B.M., therefore, octahedral geometry has been suggested for this complex¹⁴⁻²⁰. The various ligand field parameters viz. $10 Dq$, λ and LFSE for this copper complex, have been calculated and the values are : 13305 cm^{-1} , $(-)$ 615 cm^{-1} and $95.45 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

(ii) *Complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with 3-nitrobenzylidene-4-aminoacetanilide (NAA) :*

The IR spectrum of the ligand showed band at 1620 cm^{-1} . This band has shifted to $1605 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes, indicating participation of azomethine group in complexation⁸⁻¹⁰. An intense band at 1645 cm^{-1} in the ligand due to the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ (ketonic) vibration shifts lower $1635 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. This shift in $\text{C}=\text{O}$ vibration in complexes clearly suggests the participation of oxygen of anilide group in complexation. A broad band around $3440 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of complexes is assignable to ν_{stret} of water. The $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ vibrations are verified to exist by the appearance of new weak bands in the spectra of complexes at 515 ± 10 and $470 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively¹¹⁻¹⁶.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex exhibits two bands at 14530 and 19450 cm^{-1} , assignable to $^4T_{1g}(F) - ^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and $^4T_{1g}(F) - ^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively¹⁴⁻²⁰. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 5.05 B.M. The value of ligand field parameters $10 Dq$, β , λ and LFSE are 8072 cm^{-1} , 558 cm^{-1} , 0.49 , $(-)$ 601 cm^{-1} and 96.4 kJ mol^{-1} respectively. These findings in association with μ_{eff} value are in favour of an octahedral geometry^{2,11,14,16,19,23} for the Co^{II} complex. The Ni^{II} complex shows the absorption bands at 11330 , 19320 and 23110 cm^{-1} which have tentatively been assigned to $^3A_{2g}(F) - ^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), $^3A_{2g}(F) - ^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and $^3A_{2g}(F) - ^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) respectively. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 3.14 B.M. The electronic spectra and magnetic moment data suggests the octahedral geometry^{11,14,19,23} for this complex. The values of various ligand field parameters $10 Dq$, B , β , λ , ν_2/ν and LFSE are 11330 , 562.6 cm^{-1} , $(-)$ 310 , 0.52 , 1.7

and 135.31 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively which support the same view. The Cu^{II} complex gives a broad band at 14405 cm⁻¹. The nature of the band corresponds to transition ${}^2E_g - {}^2T_{2g}$. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 1.95 B.M. The value of ligand field parameters 10 *Dq*, λ and LFSE are 14405 cm⁻¹, (-) 916 cm⁻¹ and 172 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively, favouring an octahedral geometry for this complex¹⁵⁻²¹.

(iii) *Complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with furfurylidene-2-nitroaniline (FNA) :*

The IR spectral band in the ligand at 1628 cm⁻¹ has shifted to lower side (1615 ± 10 cm⁻¹) in complexes suggesting the >C=N- group participation in coordination with metal ion⁴. The furan C-O-C moiety band at 1190 cm⁻¹ in the ligand, appears at about 1160 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicating the involvement of C-O-C group in coordination⁸⁻¹³. Thermal data suggest the presence of water (Table 2). The IR bands in complexes appear at about 3450 ± 10 and 775 ± 5 cm⁻¹, which are assignable to ν_{OH} stretching and rocking modes of water respectively. The new weak bands in the spectra of complexes at 510 ± 5 cm⁻¹ and 455 ± 10 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} bonding respectively^{8-13,18-21}.

The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex shows two bands at 16210 and 20000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) - {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) - {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) respectively. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 4.95 B.M. The value of ligand field parameters 10 *Dq*, *B*, β , λ and LFSE are 9005 cm⁻¹, 620 cm⁻¹, 0.55, (-) 613 cm⁻¹ and 107.55 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. These findings are in favour of an octahedral geometry¹⁴⁻²⁰. In Ni^{II} complex, the absorption bands at 10490, 18210 and 26535 cm⁻¹ have tentatively been assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) - {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) - {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) - {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) respectively. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 3.10 B.M. The electronic spectrum and magnetic moment data suggest the octahedral geometry^{2,11,14,16} for this complex. The values of various ligand field parameters 10 *Dq*, *B*, β , ν_3/ν_2 , λ and LFSE are as 10490 cm⁻¹, 885 cm⁻¹, 0.81, 1.7, (-) 250 and 125.28 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively^{14,20}.

The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex gives a

band at 14220 cm⁻¹ corresponding to transition ${}^2E_g - {}^2T_{2g}$. The magnetic moment value for this complex is 1.92 B.M. The various ligand field parameters viz. 10 *Dq*, λ and LFSE have been calculated and values are as 14220 cm⁻¹, (-) 780 cm⁻¹ and 169.82 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The electronic band position and ligand field parameters are in good agreement with the octahedral geometry of the Cu^{II} complex^{8,12,15,19,23}.

ESR studies : The ESR spectrum of [Cu(NAA)Cl₂].2H₂O complex has been recorded on an X-band at a frequency of 9.07 GHz at a magnetic field strength of 2000 ± 4000 Gauss at 300 K. The ESR spectrum of the complex exhibits a Lorentzian type of peak. The value of the ESR parameters viz. g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , *G* and Δg are 2.1786, 2.1212, 2.1403, 1.4815 and 0.0574 respectively^{2,8,16,19-21}.

Antimicrobial activity : All the three Schiff bases and their metal complexes have been evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *A. fumigatus* and *A. niger* at concentrations 50 and 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ by single disc method^{23,24} using Streptomycine as control. The order of activity for Schiff bases have been found to be : NDA > NAA > FNA; while for their metal ion complexes : Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II}. The ligand NDA having three -NO₂ groups proved to be most effective against microbes, in comparison to NAA and FNA which contains only one -NO₂ group. On the basis of present studies, it has been concluded that metal-chelates are more active than the ligands or metal ions, alone (zone of inhibition for ligand FNA was 5–8 mm; for metal ion Co^{II} < 5 mm). The biocidal and biostatic activities of the bioactive compounds against microbes may be explained as, either they kill the microbes or inhibit their multiplication by blocking their active sites. A normal living cell contains the multitude of enzymes responsible for metabolic processes. A semi-permeable membrane (cytoplasmic membrane) maintains the integrity of the cellular contents and the membrane-selectively controls the passage of substances between the cell and its external environment and also at the site of some enzyme reactions. The cell wall properly provides a protective covering to the cell in addition to participating in certain physiological processes. Damage at any of these areas may initiate a number of subsequent changes leading to the death of the cell. Most

of the commonly used chemotherapeutic agents inhibit or kill, by one of the following basic mechanism – damage to cell wall or inhibition of cell wall synthesis; alteration of the permeability of the cytoplasmic membrane; alteration of the physical or chemical state of proteins and nucleic acids; inhibition of enzyme action; inhibition of protein or nucleic acid synthesis and substrate competition with an essential metabolite. The transition metal chelates may bind the microbes or their metabolites through N, O or S donors. Further they may penetrate into the cell to affect the vital parts like DNA/RNA etc., or block nutritive channels. In nature or in practice, the microbes are exclusively, neither in non-polar surroundings nor in polar surroundings, but they remain in semi-polar conditions, therefore, the coordination compounds with moderate molecular weight, become more effective^{2,4,12,22-24}.

Experimental

All the used chemicals and metal salts were of AnalaR grade. The percentage of C and N, FAB-mass and IR spectra (KBr) were recorded at SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow. Magnetic measurements were made by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra (in MeOH) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Lambda-2B spectrophotometer at our department. ESR spectra were recorded at RSIC, IIT, Mumbai. Molar conductance ($10^{-3} M$) was measured at room temperature by Elico-conductivity bridge.

Synthesis of Schiff base ligands : The Schiff bases were synthesized by adding the methanolic solution of 3-nitrobenzaldehyde/2-furfuraldehyde (0.01 mol) to the alcoholic solution of 2,4-dinitroaniline/4-aminoacetanilide/2-nitroaniline (0.01 mol) in equimolar ratio. The reaction mixture was then refluxed on a water bath for about 4–7 h. The condensation product was thoroughly washed, re-crystallized, dried and characterized. The purity of the synthesized compounds was monitored by tlc, using silica gel as an adsorbent.

Preparation of metal complexes : The metal complexes have been synthesized by mixing the methanolic solution of the appropriate metal salt $MCl_2 \cdot nH_2O$ [$M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}] (0.01 mol) to the methanolic solution of ligand (0.01 mol) in 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 ratio and the resulting mixture

was refluxed on water bath for 3–6 h. A coloured product appeared on standing and cooling the above solution. It was filtered, washed and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator followed by heating (60–80 °C) in an electric oven.

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